

Opinion

Loch Leven, long term monitoring and lake restoration. Photo by Bryan Spears

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The purpose of the World Water Quality Alliance (WWQA) is to engage and unite society to protect water quality and to redress water quality deterioration, which is one of the great challenges of the 21st Century. The foundation for the WWQA was laid in the United Nations Environment Assembly (UNEA) Resolution 3/10 on Addressing water pollution to protect and restore water-related ecosystems (UNEP/EA.3/Res.10, 2017) that requested UN Environment Programme (UNEP) to develop a global water quality assessment in collaboration with UN-Water and relevant stakeholders.

As a follow-up, UNEP and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission launched the WWQA in Ispra, Italy, on 19 September 2019 to “bring together a wide range of expertise in fields of water quality science, technology innovation, governance and diplomacy to seek solutions”.

The WWQA embodies a voluntary, multi-stakeholder network that works as a genuine partnership, an open community of practice. The WWQA focuses on improving the quality of water around the world through monitoring, analysis, research, communication and identifying solutions for the maintenance and restoration of impaired aquatic ecosystems.

The WWQA aims to provide a participatory platform for water quality assessments, issues and solutions and invites all that can play a role in protecting and improving water quality, no matter their qualifications or expertise, to join the WWQA. To do so, an email can be sent to wwqa-coordination@un.org stating which workstream/s you would like to contribute to, a short summary of your organization and how the work your organization links to the specific workstream/s of the WWQA.

The efforts of the WWQA are currently divided into 14 active workstreams:

- Baseline World Water Quality Assessment
- GlobeWQ STI Platform development
- Africa Use Case
- Capacity Development Consortium (CDCm)
- Social Engagement Platform
- Citizen data for SDG 6.3.2
- **Ecosystems**
- Friends of Groundwater
- Global Scenarios Ecosystem Health
- Scenario Analysis for the World Water Quality Assessment
- Plastics
- Water-ForCE
- Towards a Pan-African Water Quality Program (PAWaQ)
- Youth Action for World Water Quality

WWQA ECOSYSTEMS WORKSTREAM

About WWQA Ecosystems

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream was established in 2021 to support large-scale initiatives to prevent, halt and redress the destruction of our freshwater ecosystems, focusing initially on water quality management in lakes and their catchments. It is coordinated by IHE-Delft with a core group of the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, UNEP, European Joint Research Centre, Wageningen University, and the Norwegian Institute for Water Research. Strong links have been established between the WWQA

Ecosystems team and the SIL Working Group on Lake Restoration.

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream encourages an open membership behind a common goal: to assess and improve water quality with a focus on freshwater restoration. WWQA Ecosystems has a long-term ambition to support restoration strategies combining socio-economic and biophysical evidence to drive the transition from heavily polluting activities towards those that relieve stress on the aquatic environment. A key aim is to support sustainable management of freshwaters whilst releasing economic growth.

Recent WWQA Ecosystems Activities

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream hosted two sessions at the 2021 SIWI World Water Week. The sessions titled ‘Investing for Change through the World Water Quality Alliance’ were held on 24th August 2021 and on 26th August 2021. The session was awarded the SIWI Gold Standard for Diversity. The session was a first step in establishing a Global Community of Practice, with 254 registrations (Chart 1) and contributions from active restoration programmes in Chile, North America, Europe, New Zealand, India, and Africa. [Links to parallel sessions can be found here.](#)

The SIWI 2021 sessions developed the Top 5 Actions required to transform lake management in the coming years:

1. Restoration must now move to embrace both ecological and social benefits.
2. National institutional capacities must be enhanced to accelerate uptake and implementation.

Fig. 1 Analytics of participation in sessions hosted by WWQA Ecosystems Workstream at the 2021 SIWI World Water Week.

3. New partnerships must be fostered to deliver better integration of policies and sectoral interests.
4. Monitoring, assessment, and future scenario projections must be embedded within restoration investments to underpin long-term evidence-based decision-making.
5. Enabling conditions must be created to de-risk and enhance investment in sustainable lake management, with an active role for new public-private partnerships.

Fig. 2 Responses from the lake management practitioner community indicating the global importance of multiple pressures. Only responses indicating ‘moderate’ or ‘severe’ impacts of pressures are listed.

The WWQA Ecosystems Workstream also organised a special session at the latest SIL conference in Berlin. The session ‘Sustainable Freshwater Management in the 21st Century’ took place on August 9th 2022 and hosted 24 oral contributions from 12 different countries.

WWQA Ecosystems through UNEP and JRC, conducted a [GLOBAL SURVEY OF LAKE RESTORATION IN PRACTICE](#) collating experiences of the lake restoration practitioner community, attracting 179 questionnaire returns with coverage from 64 countries until the SIL2022 conference. Preliminary analyses indicate that many pressures are pervasive, but that nutrients and climate change are perceived to be most important globally (Fig. 2). General messages to date include that:

- poor understanding of pressures and their effects is perceived to be one of the most important reasons behind failure in lake restoration,
- most restoration programmes do not consider future climate change in their long-term planning, and,
- novel pressures will call for new approaches to lake restoration, both in setting restoration targets and devising restoration strategies.

This survey aims to compile experiences gained from real restoration of lakes in order to identify the leading causes for failure/success of lake restoration and to draw recommendations for future initiatives. The

survey is available in 5 languages, and is still open to receive answers. To access the survey please visit the website at this address: <https://forms.office.com/tr/uFnKsxlT5M>

The survey analysis will be disseminated in the scientific literature, to a wider audience, and will serve as input for a White Paper to identify key issues and implementation of actions for better coordination to protect and restore water quality in lakes.

Want to contribute to the work of WWQA Ecosystems?

The WWQA Ecosystems Core Group convenes the wider Membership, reviewing, and synthesising their experiences on the challenges and benefits of lake restoration. This wider membership helps us to identify opportunities for enhancing coordination of action in the area of lake restoration and relevant policies, and, conducting awareness raising campaigns across sectors on the multiple benefits of effective sustainability-based restoration of freshwater ecosystems.

[More information about the WWQA Ecosystems Workstream can be found at here.](#)

To express an interest in contributing to WWQA Ecosystems please send an email to:

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Reither See – Austria. Photo by Miquel Lüring